

D.6.8 Design of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising activities

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-ROLES tasks

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Task 8.4	Online Media presence.

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GEARING-ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectoral collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities and awareness-raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
OBU	Oxford Brookes University
STEM	Science, technology, engineering and mathematics
T	Task
UDEUSTO	Universidad de la Iglesia de Deusto Entidad Religiosa
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document provides information about the audio and video material which is part of the GEARING-Roles project, and its position within other WPs and Tasks. The specific objectives of the series of gender-sensitive print and online media for awareness raising include:

- (i) maximising visibility and raising awareness of the project and its activity to target stakeholders and the wider public;
- (ii) engaging target groups and key actors across project activities;
- (iii) sharing information and raising awareness about challenging problems and solutions with regard to gender equality.

Within the project, a key objective is the deconstruction of gender roles. The project aims to do this by raising awareness of what these gender roles are and how internalised and unchallenged behaviours, perceptions, and practices related to gender perpetuate gender inequalities. The GEAR tool illustrates how implicit bias operates, and encourages organisations to challenge cultural stereotypes and reconsider the reasons behind individual and institutional decisions. With this in mind, GEARING-Roles considers that a viable approach to tackling implicit bias is to understand the sociology and psychology of gender roles, challenge these roles, and move towards eliminating their effects on equality. GEARING-Roles will, thus, reinforce a gender-sensitive perspective in research, and research institutions, including in their everyday teaching and campus life.

In order to achieve these goals, GEARING-Roles will develop three actions:

1. Identify, gather and collect existing initiatives and good practices undertaken by project partners, and other projects to raise awareness on gender roles and gender equality through the use of multimedia. These materials will be shared in the Project social media channels and/or the Project YouTube channel. Besides, these videos could be used for teaching and fostering gender mainstreaming in research.
 - Examples:
 - INSPIRA Video: <https://youtu.be/-ShBktgkHxk>
 - UDEUSTO gender Interdisciplinary platform: <https://youtu.be/G3WJSy1HSn0>
2. Focus on advocacy activities on campuses and outside to mobilise support from different stakeholders. GEARING-Roles will identify and gather relevant innovative materials and resources to raise awareness about gender equality. In particular, it will discuss the causes and consequences of the limited representation of women leaders in decision-making boards and selection committees, while, at the same time, highlighting examples of best practices in European institutions. Resources and efforts will also be directed towards awareness raising activities and the training of key and relevant stakeholders, further strengthening our networks and alliances in the implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).
3. Develop our own resources to be shared online and displayed on wide screens at events. These will include:
 - project storytelling: explaining aims and objectives of the project in an engaging and accessible way. Storytelling is a powerful tool for inspiring action and change and influencing thought leaders, funders, decision-makers and especially young people. In the

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digital era, the shape and delivery of stories has shifted dramatically. Effective storytelling will inspire audiences, particularly young people, by creating human connection and emotional resonance with gender topics. Stories can be used to share lessons learnt, successes and failures with other actors and key audiences. These materials can be easily integrated in teaching, disseminating and community engagement activities.

- short informational videos on gender-related data, which will be developed based on the literature review conducted in WP3's environment and cultural assessment, and uploaded on social media platforms. Learning experiences, progress, challenges, and strategies of the project will also be presented.

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1. Gender-sensitive resources

These resources span several Tasks within WP6, namely T6.3 on gender-sensitive methodology, T6.4 on gender-sensitive teaching resources, in addition to T6.6 on community engagement. They also contribute to WP5 T5.4, related to awareness-raising of causes and consequences of women's limited representation and understanding of gender stereotyping, and T8.4, relating to online media presence.

1.1. Audio-visual media for awareness raising: gender, innovation and entrepreneurship

The first set of materials relates to exploration around gender, innovation and entrepreneurship. This is key in translating research into products and services and particularly relates to STEM subjects which are more likely than other disciplines to result in commercialisation opportunities. It also relates strongly to the aspects of research-related careers and institutional change which are a focus of the GEARING-Roles project.

There are fewer women than men within the entrepreneurship ecosystem in Europe and beyond (Elsevier, 2017; Jarboe et al, 2018). This is often attributed to the underrepresentation of women in STEM subjects, particularly a 'leaky pipeline' which sees representation of women decrease in higher positions and fewer move on to commercializing their inventions (Rosa and Dawson, 2006; Whittington and Smith-Doerr, 2005). Recent research (Griffiths et al, 2020) has demonstrated that women often face additional challenges, particularly related to securing funding, juggling work-life balance, a lack of role models and relatable mentors and negative stereotypes about women scientists. The media provided explore these issues, both from a research perspective and the perspectives of women successfully working as/with entrepreneurs. The structural issues that might be addressed to enable more women to exploit their research are also explored.

The first of these media is a video (Video 1) entitled 'Inclusive Innovation: Women, STEM and Entrepreneurship'. The media presents an opportunity for some of the women to share their stories and experiences in an accessible and engaging way, and allows them to explain what inspires them. The women introduce themselves, with two being entrepreneurs who have established successful spinout companies in STEM, and one the role of supporting research commercialisation and investment at a prominent UK university. The entrepreneurs describe their experiences and thoughts in response to questions about what motivates them, with all three giving responses on what makes a great entrepreneur and how to improve women's representation in spinouts and as founders. All describe the importance of mentors or role models in achieving success and the types of structural support which universities and state structures might provide to encourage more women into entrepreneurship.

The second video (Video 2) is called 'Women, STEM and Inclusive Innovation'. The video begins by explaining that lack of gender diversity in the innovation ecosystem means missing out on the talents of women or underrepresented groups and limiting the possibilities in regards to the innovations that can be produced. There can also be serious social consequences, such as the three-point seatbelt system, which took over four decades to account for the safety of pregnant women and the unborn child. Professor Londa Schiebinger makes a compelling case about the importance of integrating sex and gender analysis into research and development processes, which is not just about 'fixing the women', but also bringing greater numbers into STEM subjects ('fixing the numbers'). She also advocates promoting gender equality in all career levels through structural change in HEIs and through national policies ('fixing the institutions') and integrating sex and gender analysis into science

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and technology ('fixing the knowledge'). This is explained in the context of an EPSRC-funded project on gender and spinouts that seeks to improve the access of women to commercialising their research and developing their innovations.

Screenshots that illustrate the videos are also provided in Annexes 1 and 2 and the videos are available via [\[link\]](#).

1.2. PowerPoint and video for awareness-raising: gender and economics

This set of materials relates to the subject of economics through a gender lens, with economics being a particular domain where women are under-represented in research, teaching and learning, as well as professionally.

The first media is a PowerPoint presentation entitled 'Gender and Economics'. Feminist economics is the study of economics and economies, with a concentration on the role that social constructs of gender play in everyday life. It has historically focused on topics including the gender pay gap, unpaid labour and fertility and reproduction. The core aspects of feminist economics can be divided by the factors of production, i.e., labour, capital and technology.

There are considerable gender differences in pay, employment level and speciality in work. Women face significant discrimination in promotion to high-status roles or in accessing sectors dominated by men. Men can also face discrimination when accessing women-dominated sectors, although these are usually less well paid. From the perspective of capital, there is a profound gender difference in salary bargaining, in which men are more confident in proposing higher salaries and requesting regular increases. Women also face discrimination in access to capital and credit, both by investors (for entrepreneurship) and by banks (for loans).

On a global scale, women have lower levels of access to technologies, higher rates of harassment whilst online and lower rates of digital literacy due to a gender digital divide. Fertility and reproduction are often cited as one of the main reasons for women's disadvantage in the labour market. Key interdependencies in the fertility – employment trade off often explored include periods of care for children during which women may not be able to work; labour market skills being unable to accumulate/depreciating during this time; anticipation of having children constraining women's career choices and the expectations that women will perform unpaid domestic labour when they re-enter the workplace.

The presentation concludes that to have a gender perspective in economics, we need to ensure that women are represented throughout the academic ranks; that inequalities of gender and other forms of marginalised groups are embedded in teaching; and that awareness is raised about other research areas of economics outside political and financial economics, such as labour markets, development economics and behavioural science. It aims to:

- (i) Promote a discussion the key factors leading to gender inequalities in economics;
- (ii) Deepen understandings of the consequences of societal gendered constraints on economics
- (iii) Consider what can be done to promote a gender perspective in economics

Screenshots of the presentation are provided in Annex 3 and the PowerPoint slides available on the GEARING ROLES site [\[link\]](#).

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The presentation is supported by a video (Video 3 – gender and economics) and is intended for use in discussion and teaching. The video is available [link] and screenshots of the video are provided in Annex 4.

1.3. Gender-sensitive visual aids for awareness raising: exploring and creating feminist landscapes under Covid

Restrictions on travel and movement across the consortium partners’ countries constrained advocacy activities on campuses and outside of individuals’ homes. This limited the ability to mobilise support from different stakeholders, as well as opportunities to strengthen networks and alliances. In the absence of these, alternative methods were explored to stimulate engagement.

A key activity was a set of ‘feminist heritage walks’ that some members of the OBU team undertook, first in pairs (to comply with UK Covid restrictions), then later as a team. These heritage walks were based on the ‘Women on the March’ route (Bradley, 2018), which was devised to showcase and celebrate the suffrage movement that contributed significantly to the political and social life in Oxford early in the 20th century.

Bartlett (2020) describes walking as “a form of movement and activism... a productive methodology, ... politics, and form of embodiment that maps routes and moves us through space that is highly amenable to the generation of feminist sites of heritage”(p1020). It also “connects us to feminist intellectual legacies, as well as producing forms of sociality, relation, resonance, and reflection manifested in **place**” (ibid). Walking was therefore felt to be an appropriate activity for connecting with local heritage to better understand Oxford’s feminist history. It also aimed to support a growing movement recognising that there are far fewer monuments and statues of women compared to men and that this sends a strong message about the value placed on women.¹ These ‘lockdown feminist walks’ also gave visibility to other types of landmark which are not celebrated through plaques or statues. These included sites of organised meetings about feminist activities, informal sites (e.g., cafes) for political meetings, clubs and meeting places or places where notable women have studied (often in defiance of contemporary conventions). There were also sites of protest or acts of rebellion to be visited, and we were mindful that organized walks and marches have long been adopted as a form of feminist protest (Reger, 2015). Other consortium members’ work also served as inspirational, for example, the ‘Feminist Walking in the City’ event run by Sabanci University,² which asked ‘what do we see when we look at the city?’, and their ‘Curious Steps: Gender and Memory Walks’ which “makes possible the ‘discovery’ and sharing of many hidden stories”.³

When the entire OBU team were able to meet face-to-face (under socially-distanced conditions permitted by government guidelines), they took part in a group walk. This was used as an opportunity to meet and share the experience of exploring landmarks in the city of Oxford relating to its feminist past. During the walk, the t-shirts designed as a travelling exhibition were worn. These display the set of designs that were developed as part of D6.6 to draw attention to women’s achievements across academic disciplines and the economy and society since the turn of the 21st century. The photographs from these walks are shown in Annex 5.

¹ See, for example, <https://www.invisiblewomen.org.uk/>. This site provides a space for the public to submit details of the statues in their city to collate statistics on the prevalence of women versus men.

² <https://gearingroles.eu/feminist-walking-the-city/>

³ <https://sugender.sabanciuniv.edu/en/curious-steps-gender-and-memory-walks>

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The images of the travelling t-shirt exhibition often contrasted with some of the monolithic and historical buildings and structures that formed the backdrop to the walk. In the past, these structures have been the sites of women’s education and political enlightenment and, through meetings, rallies and political campaigns, a place to raise their voices. The t-shirts were also a novel way to exhibit and create images promoting diversity and inclusion outside the classroom and among different stakeholders, engaging with one another face-to-face (though restricted to meeting outdoors) and the public passers-by on the day.

Against this backdrop, a pilot community engagement activity was run to coincide with Women’s History Month 2021, in conjunction with Oxford International Women’s Festival.⁴ The Festival, which has been in existence for over 30 years, moved online for a second year. The 2021 theme was ‘Women Creating Landscapes’. A series of tweets was set up with the hashtags #creatingfeministlandscapes and #creatinglandscapes to encourage women to record and feed back to others on their surroundings during Women’s History Month in lockdown. A series of tweets is shown in Annex 6. This activity also overlapped with some of the paired feminist heritage walks mentioned in the section above, which were used as an opportunity to photograph and share ‘landscapes’.

As lockdown restrictions ease, we aim to build on the two ‘heritage walks’ and the ‘creating landscapes’ pilot further as a community engagement activity. This will allow us to take advantage of renewed opportunities for face-to-face activities. These are unlikely to resume in full for some time but will instead support some types of hybrid activities that draw on online sources alongside tentative and socially-distanced re-emergence. These include (though would not be limited to):

- Including photographs collected during the heritage walks in follow-up activities, both online through a follow-up **social media** campaign and, potentially, face-to-face with students and academic staff as an addition to the **travelling exhibition** (once Covid restrictions permit).
- Encouraging GEPI partners and other stakeholders to join in with these activities in ways that suit the developing changes in their environments. The spaces they can safely inhabit and where they might meet in the future, online or otherwise will differ from country to country as each emerges from their own Covid restrictions at a different rate. However, approaches to using materials that can be online or face-to-face in different contexts will accommodate these needs. In addition, where GEPI partners have already developed walking activities, we will collaborate to share experiences and develop further the engagement opportunities.

⁴ <https://oiwf.org/>

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Annex 1 – Screenshots of video 1 - Inclusive Innovation - women, STEM and entrepreneurship

Figure 1 screenshot of video 1

Figure 2 screenshot of video 1

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Figure 3 screenshot of video 1

Figure 4 screenshot of video 1

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Figure 5 screenshot of video 1

Figure 6 screenshot of video 1

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Figure 7 screenshot of video 1

Figure 8 screenshot of video 1

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Annex 2 – Screenshots of Video 2 – Women, STEM and Inclusive Innovation

Figure 9 screenshot video 2

Figure 10 screenshot video 2

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Figure 11 screenshot video 2

- THE THREE-POINT SEATBELT WAS FIRST DEVELOPED IN 1959.
- IT TOOK OVER FOUR DECADES FOR THE TECHNOLOGY TO ACCOUNT FOR THE SAFETY OF PREGNANT WOMEN.
- IN 2002, LAURA THACKARAY ADAPTED THE TECHNOLOGY FOR WOMEN IN A WAY THAT NO MALE ENGINEER HAD THOUGHT TO DO PREVIOUSLY.

Figure 12 screenshot video 2

IT'S NOT ABOUT 'FIXING THE WOMEN'

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Figure 13 screenshot video 2

Figure 14 screenshot video 2

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Annex 3 – Screen shots of PowerPoint presentation – Gender and economics

Figure 15 screenshot of Power-Point presentation

Gender and Economics

Dr Anne Laure Humbert, with contributions from Geena Whiteman
Centre for Diversity Policy Research and Practice
Oxford Brookes University

Figure 16 screenshot of Power-Point presentation

Objectives/Goals

- Promote a discussion the key factors leading to gender inequalities in economics.
- Deepen understandings of the consequences of societal gendered constraints on economics.
- Consider what can be done to promote a gender perspective in economics.

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Figure 17 screenshot of Power-Point presentation

What is feminist economics?

- The study of economics and economies, with a concentration on the role that social constructs of gender play in everyday life.
- Historically, feminist economics research has focused on topics such as:
 - Gender Pay Gap
 - Unpaid Labour
 - Fertility and Reproduction

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Figure 18 screenshot of Power-Point presentation

- The goal of feminist economics is to *“enhance the well-being of children, women and men in local, national and transnational communities”* (Sharpe, 2020).
- However, the field in itself is stuck with unconscious bias, outdated assumptions and inequality of access between genders.
- Many women are put off the study of economics due to the overarching stereotype that economics is the study of finance
- This is a disproportionately large aspect of undergraduate studies
- Men entering the field are not initiated into the field with a gender lens on research, nor do they consider intersections of inequalities such as gender, race, sexuality and ethnicity.

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Annex 4 – Screenshots of video 3 – Gender and economics

Figure 19 screenshot of video 3

Figure 20 screenshot of video 3

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Figure 21 screenshot of video 3

Figure 22 screenshot of video 3

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Figure 23 screenshot of video 3

Figure 24 screenshot of video 3

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Annex 5 – Photographs of feminist heritage walks

Figure 25 photograph 1 – former home of dedicated women’s suffrage supporter

Figure 26 photograph 2 – Martyr’s Memorial and popular suffragette meeting place

Figure 27 photograph 3 – site of suffragist procession 1913

Figure 28 photograph 4 – Oxford Union, site of early debates on suffrage

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Figure 29 photograph 5 – former common room for women HE students (between 1898 & 1920)

Figure 30 photograph 6 – former office of Oxford Women's Suffrage Society

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Figure 31 photograph 7 – former site of Women’s Social and Political Union

Figure 32 photograph 8 – Oxford Town Hall (site of suffragette meetings)

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Annex 6 – Tweets #CreatingLandscapes

Figure 33 Tweet 1

Figure 34 Tweet 2

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Figure 35 Tweet 3

Figure 36 Tweet 4

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Figure 37 Tweet 5

Figure 38 Tweet 6

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